

Quality Management in Higher Education In India

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Abstract: The aim of the paper is to understand the relevance of higher education in a globalized competitive world of which India too has been active part off.

With economic reforms of Liberalization privatization and globalization India has no doubt become a global player in world geo politics as well as the world economy.

India being the 7th largest Economy in nominal terms and 3rd largest economy in terms of purchasing power no doubt is a force to be reckoned with. However to truly emerge as a geopolitical and economic force to be reckoned with and take its rightful place in the world as a worthy leader, India no doubt has to focus on its Educational system particularly her higher education.

The paper tries to analyse the importance of higher education in making India world leader in a scenario where in India faces herself in thick of things in a ever dynamic world full of uncertainties, insecurities and rapid competition in every sense of the word.....along with it added menace of adverse effects of climate change.

Key Words: Higher Education, relevance, Highly Competitive world, Climate change

1.Introduction: If at all one has to to ensure one remedy for plethora of problems that mother India faces be it, so called over population, transition to clean sources of energy, women empowerment so that better half of our population is not left behind, upgrading our defence capabilities so that our interesting neighbours maintain a healthy distance, to ensure sustainable development and evolution smart cities along with smart villages, to lead the 3rd world countries, to ensure socio economic just society in changing world along with meaningful contribution to tackle the adverse impact of climate change.....India needs to utilise her resources in best possible manner.....more importantly she needs qualified manpower to give her rightful ambition proper direction.

To ensure which India has to give due emphasis on higher education. Of course due emphasis must definitely be given to primary and secondary education.....for without proper foundation no great castles can be built.

However in this paper we focus predominantly on higher education and its relevance and importance in the context of changing times and demands of a dynamic world.

2.Objectives of the study:

- a) To find out the present condition of higher education system in India....challenges and remedies there in.
- b).To understand the relevance of Higher education with regard to various challenges that India faces along with the world in which she finds herself highly integrated particularly after introducing Economic Reforms of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization.

3.Present scenario:

India's higher educational system is third largest in the world next only to United States and China. The main governing body at the tertiary level is the University Grants Commission, which enforces its standards, advises the government, and helps coordinate between the

centre and the state. Accreditation for higher learning is overseen by 15 autonomous institutions established by the University Grants Commission (UGC). As per 2011 census around 8.15%(68 million) of Indians are graduates. The union territories of Delhi and Chandigarh top the list with 24% and 26% of their population being graduates.

As of 2016, India has 799 universities, with a break up of 44 central universities, 540 state universities, 122 deemed universities, 90 private universities, 5 institutions established and functioning under the State Act, and 75 Institutes of National Importance which include AIIMS, IIT's and NIT's among others.

Market Size :

The education sector in India is poised to witness major growth in the years to come as India will have world’s largest tertiary-age population and second largest graduate talent pipeline globally by the end of 2020. As of now the education market is worth US\$ 100 billion. Currently, higher education contributes 59.7 per cent of the market size, school education 38.1 per cent, pre-school segment 1.6 per cent, and technology and multi-media the remaining 0.6 per cent. Higher education system in India has undergone rapid expansion.

Currently, India’s higher education system is third largest in the world enrolling over 70 million students(2016) while in less than two decades, India has managed to create additional capacity for over 40 million students. At present, higher education sector witnesses spending of over Rs 46,200 crore (US\$ 6.96 billion), and it is expected to grow at an average annual rate of over 18 per cent to reach Rs 232,500 crore (US\$ 35.03 billion) in next 10 years.

4. Challenges:

i) Lack of quality and global competitiveness: Despite India having the third largest education system,

the best ranking Indian university namely Indian Institute of Science ran research influence score and research ks in cohort of 251 to 300...a slip from 201 to 250 group as per Times Higher Education World University Rankngs .

IISc slid largely due to drops in its research influence score and research income, the ranking survey said. While the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Bombay continues to be in the 351-400 band, IIT Delhi and IIT Kanpur have dropped by one grouping—from 401-500 to 501-600.

ii)High student to Teacher ratio.

This systematically ensures that the teacher is not able to give adequate attention to all the students which no doubt adversely impacts the learning outcomes.

As in the chart we can see that, India has the almost double the teacher pupil ratio as compared to the world. This is even more so evident in case of primary education.

This is a very grave cause of concern....since if students are not given adequate care in primary level and when their foundations and bases are weak they can hardly be expected do well in higher education if at all they make it to higher education.

iii) Financing – The inability of the state to fund the expanding higher education system has resulted in the rapid growth of private higher education. In addition, diminished governmental financial support adversely affects small and rural educational institutions. A growing number of public institutions are forced to resort to self-financing courses and high tuition costs. The private sector’s primary modes of financing include donations, capitation fees and exorbitant fee rates. This in turn limits general accessibility to higher education, by catering to only an elite few.

Year	Private in Medical (%Seats)	Private in Engineering (%Seats)
1960	7	15
1970	12	22
1980	11	42
1990	26	58
2000	29	82
2003	42	86

iv) Enrolment – As of 2007, only around 11% of the 18 – 23 year old population of India, is enrolled in higher education. On the whole, India has an enrolment rate of 9% which is similar to that of other lower middle income countries. The population that is enrolled in higher education consists largely of urban metropolitan dwellers. Rural enrolment in higher education is very low

v) Accreditation - Driven by market opportunities and entrepreneurial zeal, many institutions are taking advantage of the lax regulatory environment to offer 'degrees' not approved by Indian authorities, and many institutions are functioning as pseudo non-profit organisations, developing sophisticated financial methods to siphon off the 'profits'. Regulatory authorities like UGC and AICTE have been trying to extirpate private universities that run courses with no affiliation or recognition. Students from rural and semi-urban background often fall prey to these institutes and colleges.

vi) Mismatch between theory and practise: To begin with rote learning approach stifles off creativity among students. Moreover the outdated syllabus that the students are forced to endure doesn't ensure that they get good jobs.

In fact according to a reputed Delhi based Employment solutions company ‘Aspiring Minds’ in a survey conducted among 1,50,000 engineering graduates hardly 7% were found to be employable.

Among other graduates hardly 47% were employable. According to the HRD ministry, India has 6,214 engineering and technology institutions which are enrolling 2.9 million students. Around 1.5 million engineers are released into the job market every year. But the dismal state of higher education in India ensures that they simply do not have adequate skills to be employed.

vii) No accountability among Govt. Lecturers and Politicization: Among Govt lecturers there is no link between their performance and pay hence they take a very casual approach to their profession thereby undermining the future of the nation.

Our university system is, in many parts, in a state of disrepair... In almost half the districts in the country, higher education enrollments are abysmally low, almost two-third of our universities and 90 per cent of our colleges are rated as below average on quality parameters... I am concerned that in many states university appointments, including that of vice-chancellors, have been politicised and have become subject to caste and communal considerations, there are complaints of favouritism and corruption. — Prime Minister Manmohan Singh in 2007.

viii) Increasing instances of sexual harassment: Their is genuine degradation of morals in Indian society. This is very well reflected in our educational institutions. According to Ministry of Human Resource Development there has been 50% increase in the cases of sexual harassment in academic year 2016-17 as compared to 2015-16

5. Remedies:

i) Allowing foreign reputed institutions to establish their branches in India: Reputed Universities like Stanford, Harvard, Oxford and MIT must be allowed to establish their branches in India. They must be incentivised to do as such. This shall not only bring a more refined approach to learning but shall also make our own universities revamp their system to stay relevant in the market.

ii) Measures to regulate student pupil ratio: Guidelines should be in place to regulate student pupil ratio. Its high time Government also brought accountability mechanisms in government schools. The govt. Teachers salary must be linked with their performance to ensure Govt schools and colleges stay relevant.

iii) Strict Enforcement of rules and regulations : Annual rounds must be undertaken by UGC and other accreditation authorities to ensure that unregistered colleges and universities do not play with the fate of students.

iv) Industry Academia partnership: Boards like UGC, NCERT, CBSE, AICTE etc while making syllabus should take all stakeholders on board especially industry so that relevant skills are taught to students.

Moreover syllabus must be revised as frequently as possible so that it stays relevant to the changing times.